

Dynamics of epiphytic lichen communities in an industrial area of Portugal

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Abstract: Aim of this work is a study of the dynamics of the epiphytic lichen flora after the establishment of an industrial complex, based on observations of permanent quadrats, over a period of twenty years, and on the measurement of cover and distribution of lichen thalli using Geographic Information System tools. In order to detect affinities between relevés with similar composition and various environmental variables, Canonical Correspondence Analysis was used. The conclusion was that the percentage of species cover decreased, particularly that of fruticose lichens, leading to a homogenization of the vegetation and to a predominance of *Parmotrema reticulatum*.

Introduction

Epiphytic lichens have been used in many air pollution studies, both in cities (Sérgio & Bento-Pereira 1981, Nimis 1986) and in industrial areas (Jones et al. 1981, Garty & Hagemeyer 1988). A major field of research is the mapping of lichen communities, because they reflect relationships between variations in the flora and specific air pollutants (Van Dobben & Ter Braak 1999, Sim-Sim et al. 2000). An alternative approach is to measure the concentrations of the pollutant in the lichen thallus, and relate them to those in the atmosphere (Nimis 1999). Most of these studies however were limited to short periods and most without base-line data established before the installation of the pollution source.

Lichens have been shown to be sensitive to a wide range of natural and man-made environmental conditions such as phorophytes, macroclimate and microclimate, management practices and the competitive power of each species

(Barkman 1958, Wolseley & Pryor 1999). In studies of lichen community, two techniques were mostly followed, the first is to trace the outline of a thallus on transparent plastic sheets and, after some months or years, retrace the same thallus (Bedeneau, 1982). The second is to photograph and make measurements from enlarged photographic prints (John & Dale 1991).

Aim of this work is to study changes in the composition of the epiphytic lichen flora, based on observations on permanent quadrats over a period of twenty years, in an industrial area near the SW Portuguese coast. The study was based on the measurement of cover and distribution of lichen thalli using Geographic Information System Software. Two surveys were carried out, in 1976-1986 and in 1997-1998, of 65 sites. The first period corresponds to the installation and start of operation of the industrial complex, which comprises a major power plant, several refineries and chemical industries. During the second period it was possible to find 28 phorophytes (in 16 localities) with the original fixed quadrats, which allowed to follow the dynamics of these communities. The study was complemented by floristic surveys carried out in the two periods (Jones 1983, Carvalho et al. 1999).

Study area

The area, situated on the SW coast of Portugal, with the major urban center being Sines, is a gently undulating coastal plain, delimited inland by the Serra of Grândola, which lies parallel to the coast (Figure 1). The climatic data show an average temperature of 16°C, relative humidity of 80-85%, and average annual rainfall of 600 mm, largely restricted to winter and spring. The prevailing winds are from the NW, with occasional storms from the SW. Sedimentary or metamorphic rocks are prevailing, and soils are of podzols or cambisols type.

An industrial complex was installed in the late seventies, consisting mainly on a coal-fired power plant, an oil refinery, a petrochemical plant, and smaller installations. Also a motorway complex was built at that time, and a port, where important amounts of fossil fuels (coal and crude oil) are unloaded from ships. Coal is transported by a mechanical runner to the power plant complex, or conveyed elsewhere by railway.

Material and methods

Relevés of cryptogamic epiphytic vegetation

A total of 65 sites were initially selected to carry out relevés of epiphytic cryptogamic in quadrats (20x10 cm), marked mainly on two tree species, olive (*Olea europaea*) and fig (*Ficus carica*). Other dominant tree species in the area, like pine, eucalyptus or cork oaks, were avoided because of frequent loss or removal of their bark. Three quadrats were signalized at each site, when possible on different trees, and the vegetation was recorded by tracing the outlines of lichen thalli on plastic sheets. Each site was visited three times between 1977 and 1984, and again in 1997-1998. During the last visit, only ca. 25% of the original quadrats were identified, totaling 16 sites (Figure 1). The loss of quadrats was mainly because of growth of bark, covering initial marks, or cut down of branches

Figure 1: Map showing the location of sites and some other features of the study area.

where quadrats were placed.

The outlines of lichen thalli went through a quantification process, in order to determine the cover area. The procedure involved scanning of plastic sheets, digitizing thalli outlines and quantification of thalli area, which was made using ArcView GIS software (ESRI 1998).

Statistical analysis and geographic information

The cover percentage of each lichen species was determined after adding up the thallus areas of all quadrats of each site. Also a data matrix with environmental variables was built after calculating, for all sampling sites, several geographic parameters, like latitude, altitude, distance from the coast, from factory chimneys and from main roads. This was done using Geographic Information Systems, ArcView GIS and Arc/Info (ESRI 1998, 1998a). Additional data resulted from a parallel chemical analysis of lichen thalli (Figueira et al. 1999), where the concentration of several metals and saline elements was determined. These data were submitted to Principal Component Analysis, using Andad software (CVRM 2000) and sample scores of the first three factors were taken as indexes of contamination. Such indexes were estimated and mapped in the whole of the study area, after the application of geostatistical interpolation methods. Values of these indexes on the quadrats sampling sites were recorded afterwards.

All data were analyzed by Canonical Correspondence Analysis (CCA) (Ter Braak 1986), as implemented on Canoco for Windows 4.0, in order to assess the relationship between species cover percentage and environmental variables.

Results

Determination and mapping of indexes of metal and saline contamination

The concentrations of several heavy metals (Cu, Fe, Ni, Pb, Zn), alkaline and alkaline earth metals (Na, K, Mg, Ca) and Cl were determined in lichens; these results being published elsewhere (Figueira et al. 1999). The concentration of such elements in the environment, accumulated from atmospheric deposition by the lichens, may reflect contamination from the several industries, whose known emissions range from several gases (SO_x, NO_x) to particles containing heavy metals. Other dominant elements in the atmosphere of the study area have a natural source, the sea, and their deposition may also have some influence in the distribution of lichen species.

In order to identify the main types of contamination, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was carried out on the matrix of element concentrations measured in lichens that correspond to the extracellular fraction (Figueira et al. 1999). The first two factorial planes are presented in Figure 2; elements with higher scores on the first axis are Cl, Na and Mg, while on the second are Zn and Cu. In the third axis, two poles are defined by Pb and Fe on one hand, and K and Ni on the other. The first axis can be interpreted as a salinity gradient, while in the others are represented the gradient on particular associations of the elements: Cu/Zn on the second axis; on the third, Pb/Fe for low scores and K/Ni for high scores on the axis. The sample scores on each of the axis can be used as an index of the elements associated with them.

Once the sampling points for metal analysis were not coincident with the sampling points of quadrats, it was necessary to estimate the value of the indexes given by on each of the factors, by estimating them on the whole study area, using geostatistical methods (Figure 3). The value of each factor in the quadrats sampling sites was, afterwards, used as an auxiliary environmental variable for interpretation of lichen dynamics.

Dynamics of epiphytic species as measured by cover percentage

In the 16 sites, 41 species (39 lichens and 2 bryophytes) were recorded. Table 1 reports all taxa, with the respective abbreviations.

Figure 2: First (a) and second (b) factorial planes obtained by PCA of element concentration in lichens.

Figure 3: Maps of estimated samples scores on the first three factors of the PCA with element concentration measured on lichens.

CCA depicts the species distribution, its relationships with environmental factors, and the dominance of species in each site. Alterations in the projection of each sample are very important, as they permit the identification of temporal changes at community level.

The CCA biplots of first two axes show the influence of environmental variables on the distribution of individual species (Figure 4). There is a correlation between the first axis and altitude, and distance from the coast, representing a gradient from upland sites more distant from the sea (left) to those at lower altitude, and closer to the sea (right).

The CCA ordination of species indicates, in the left part of axis 1, those species that, in general, were observed in upland sites more distant from the coast such as *Parmelia caperata*, *Pertusaria amara*, *Physcia semipinnata*, *P. tenella*, and the liverwort *Frullania dilatata*. The intermediate positions on the first axis are represented by species with a wide distribution in the study area, such as *Parmotrema hypoleucinum*, *P. reticulatum*, *Ramalina calicaris* and *Schismatomma decolorans*. These taxa were observed on olive trees (*Olea europaea*) and fig trees (*Ficus carica*). Most species located on the right side of the first axis have Atlantic affinities, mainly occurring at sites with low altitude and near to the coast (e.g. *Ramalina lusitanica*, *R. farinacea*, *R. lacera* and *R. pusilla*).

Axis 2 shows correlation with the phorophyte. The positive part, is occupied by species predominant on *Morus nigra*, *Phaeophyscia orbicularis* and the moss *Orthotrichum* sp. Their high cover values are explained by the shaded and eutrophicated conditions of the sites, as observed in the field. The negative part of this axis is occupied by species from olive and fig trees, where shade and eutrophication were less significant.

The CCA ordination of relevés revealed considerable changes in the composition of the epiphytic flora since the first survey carried out in 1977 (Figure 5). The relevés corresponding to the last sampling date, labeled with letter d, are mostly projected closer to the axis origin than those of the previous dates (with labels a, b and c), which reveals a tendency to homogenization of lichen communities, leading to the predominance of generalist species.

An exception is site 39 (*Morus nigra*), probably due to changes in the microecological conditions, related to alterations in canopy density, favoring

Table 1: Lichens recorded on the sampling quadrats placed in the study area and codes used in CCA plots.

Ccan	<i>Chrysothrix candelaris</i> (L.) J.R. Laundon
Dcan	<i>Diploicia canescens</i> (Dickson) A. Massal.
Epru	<i>Evernia prunastri</i> (L.) Ach.
Fdil	<i>Frullania dilatata</i> (L.) Dum.
Larg	<i>Lecanora argentata</i> (Ach.) Malme
Lchl	<i>Lecanora chlarotera</i> Nyl.
Llev	<i>Lecanora lividocinerea</i> Bagl.
Lrub	<i>Lecanora rubicunda</i> Bagl.
Lesp	<i>Lecanora</i> sp.
Orsp	<i>Orthotrichum</i> sp.
Pcap	<i>Parmelia caperata</i> (L.) Ach.
Psor	<i>Parmelia soledians</i> Nyl.
Psub	<i>Parmelia subrudecta</i> Nyl.
Psul	<i>Parmelia sulcata</i> Taylor
Pchi	<i>Parmotrema chinense</i> (Osbeck) Hale et Ahti
Phyp	<i>Parmotrema hypoleucinum</i> (J. Steiner) Hale
Pret	<i>Parmotrema reticulatum</i> (Taylor) M. Choisy
Pama	<i>Pertusaria amara</i> (Ach.) Nyl.
Pend	<i>Phaeophyscia endopoenicea</i> (Harm.) Moberg
Porb	<i>Phaeophyscia orbicularis</i> (Necker) Moberg
Pads	<i>Physcia adscendens</i> (Fr.) H. Olivier
Pcle	<i>Physcia clementei</i> (Sm.) Maas Gest
Psem	<i>Physcia semipinnata</i> (Gmelin) Moberg
Phsp	<i>Physcia</i> sp.
Pten	<i>Physcia tenella</i> (Scop.) DC.
Ptri	<i>Physcia tribacioides</i> Nyl.
Pgri	<i>Physconia grisea</i> (Lam.) Poelt
Pque	<i>Pyrrhospora quernea</i> (Dickson) Körber
Rcal	<i>Ramalina calicaris</i> (L.) Röhl.
Rcan	<i>Ramalina canariensis</i> J. Steiner
Rfar	<i>Ramalina farinacea</i> (L.) Ach.
Rfas	<i>Ramalina fastigiata</i> (Pers.) Ach.
Rlac	<i>Ramalina lacera</i> (With.) J.R. Laundon
Rlus	<i>Ramalina lusitanica</i> H. Magn.
Rpus	<i>Ramalina pusilla</i> Duby
rasp	<i>Ramalina</i> sp.
Sdec	<i>Schismatomma decolorans</i> (Sm.) Clauz. & Vezda
Urub	<i>Usnea rubicunda</i> Stirton
Ussp	<i>Usnea</i> sp.
Xpar	<i>Xanthoria parietina</i> (L.) Th. Fr.

shaded conditions, and an increase of eutrophication. The composition of the lichen flora is then dominated by skiophytic and eutrophication-tolerant species.

In most localities, there was a general decrease of coverage and an increase in the predominance of *Parmotrema reticulatum* mainly on the sites farther from the coast, such as sites 6, 15, 19, 21, 22, 25, 51 and 56. In other localities, closer to the coast, as in stands 25 and 27, the best represented species is *Diploicia*

Figure 5: Ordination diagram of relevés scores on axes 1 and 2, based on CCA. Shaded numbers correspond to the last sampling date.

Figure 6 presents the difference in the cover percentage in the period between the first and the third sampling dates (ca. eight years), and between the third and the fourth date (fourteen years). The picture shows a reduction of fruticose taxa during the first years, just after the installation of the industrial complex. Foliose lichens are those which showed highest variations in cover, and also a tendency to reduce their covers, although in some sites this decline was observed only between the third and fourth dates. In sites 29 and 39, cover increase of more than 10% occurred, which may be explained by the geographic location of these sites, near the coast and north of the main contamination sources, probably not affected by emissions, which are dispersed to the opposite direction by the dominant north-west winds. Crustose lichens showed, in general, small variations of coverage with some local exceptions already mentioned. These results can be explained by the lower growth rates of crustose species.

The increase of foliose species cover is mainly due to *Parmotrema*

Figure 6: Variation of cover percentage calculated for two time lags. Light bars: 1977-1984; dark bars: 1984-1997.

reticulatum, which, because of the foliose morphology, shows a higher competitive ability, in comparison to fruticose and crustose lichens, due to its capacity to spread horizontally and to grow over other species (Barkman 1958, John & Dale 1991).

In conclusion, the most evident change in the epiphytic flora, twenty years after the establishment of the industrial complex, is the reduction of cover, particularly of fruticose species, leading to a homogenization of the vegetation and to a general predominance of *P. reticulatum*. These alterations can be correlated with industrial activity, but also with modifications in microclimatic conditions in some sites, mainly due to changes in land management.

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